

Sleep Analysis: From Clinical Polysomnography to Modern Sensing Technologies

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Abstract

Sleep analysis is essential for diagnosing sleep disorders, understanding sleep patterns, and supporting personalized health management. It has evolved from labor-intensive clinical polysomnography to diverse automated approaches spanning clinical, research, and consumer domains. This survey provides a comprehensive overview of sleep monitoring technologies, algorithms, standards, as well as trends and application of personalized sleep analysis. We examine the evolution from conventional sleep monitoring technologies such as Polysomnography (PSG) to emerging wearable devices and contactless sensing technologies, and from hand-crafted features to deep learning algorithms. We summarize evolution of sleep scoring standards and review public datasets as well as clinical validation and evaluation metrics. We then focus on trends in personalized sleep analysis, including home sleep monitoring, adaptive algorithms, and the challenges in privacy and security. Finally, we outline future directions toward robust sleep analysis systems that can be integrated into real world healthcare and life.

1 Introduction

Sleep plays a fundamental role in human health, cognitive function, and overall well-being [14]. Consequently, accurate sleep analysis has become essential for diagnosing sleep disorders, understanding circadian rhythms, and enabling personalized health management. With years of continuous development, sleep analysis has evolved from labor-intensive clinical polysomnography to diverse automated approaches spanning clinical, research, and consumer domains. This survey provides a comprehensive overview of sleep monitoring technologies, algorithms for sleep staging and micro-event detection, sleep standard scoring, as well as challenges in the sleep analysis domain and future directions of personalized sleep analysis.

We first review conventional sleep monitoring technologies, focusing on gold-standard EEG-based polysomnography (PSG) [48] and its inherent limitations in clinical and

real-world settings. We then examine emerging sleep monitoring technologies, including wearable devices [49] and contactless sensing solutions [37], and compare their accuracy, sensing characteristics, and application scenarios across diverse use cases.

The survey reviews algorithms for automatic sleep staging and micro-event detection, from hand-crafted spectral pipelines to deep-learning models operating on raw PSG and wearable signals. We emphasize CNN-, RNN-, and attention-based architectures and their performance on both epoch-level staging and event-level detection.

We also examine the neurophysiological foundations of sleep architecture, including NREM-REM transitions regulated by thalamocortical and brainstem networks, and the associated micro-architectural markers such as sleep spindles, K-complexes, slow-wave oscillations, and REM-related phasic events. We further review the evolution of scoring methodologies from the classical Rechtschaffen & Kales (R&K) rules to the standardized AASM criteria, which unify stage definitions and event annotations for improved clinical and algorithmic reproducibility. We analyze the trade-offs between accuracy and practicality across different sensing modalities, validation methodologies for new sleep technologies, and the clinical significance of various sleep parameters.

Additionally, we review the emerging trends in personalized sleep analysis, with a particular focus on new sensing technologies such as home sleep monitoring [33], sleep wearable devices [32], contactless sleep monitoring [63], and adaptive algorithms [67]. Recent advances in wearable and contactless sensing technologies enable continuous sleep monitoring in real-world environment beyond research laboratory [34]. In addition, deep learning algorithms and domain adaption models have been proposed to improve the robustness and performance of sleep analysis. Building upon these developments, we systematically review the current status and future challenges of sleep analysis across sensing hardware, algorithms, and regulatory frameworks [1].

Figure 1: Various electrodes used in PSG [40]

2 Sleep Monitoring Technologies

2.1 Conventional Sleep Monitoring Technologies

Polysomnography (PSG) is regarded as the "gold standard" for the diagnosis of sleep-related breathing disorders (SRBD), such as obstructive sleep apnea (OSA). It is widely used to evaluate many other sleep pathologies, including narcolepsy and nocturnal seizures. A standard Type I PSG (attended in-laboratory polysomnography) simultaneously records multiple physiological signals to evaluate sleep stages and cardiopulmonary function, offering a level of detail not available in unattended home testing (Types II-IV).

The core components of a PSG montage include Electroencephalography (EEG), Electro-oculography (EOG), and Electromyography (EMG) [50].

For EEG, electrodes are placed on the scalp according to the International 10-20 System to capture electrical activity from the frontal, central, and occipital brain regions, as shown in Figure 2. For EOG, electrodes placed on the outer canthi monitor horizontal and vertical eye movements, which are essential to identify Rapid Eye Movement (REM) sleep and slow-rolling eye movements associated with the onset of sleep. For EMG, submental EMG is used to detect muscle atonia characteristic of REM sleep, and anterior tibialis EMG is used to detect periodic limb movements (PLMS). In addition to these, a comprehensive PSG distinguishes between types of breathing disorders using specific sensors. For example, an oronasal thermal sensor is used to detect apneas ($\geq 90\%$ airflow reduction), and a nasal pressure transducer is used for identifying hypopneas ($\geq 30\%$ airflow reduction). Additionally, respiratory inductance plethysmography (RIP) belts on the thorax and abdomen measure respiratory effort, and pulse oximetry monitors oxygen saturation (SpO_2).

However, PSG faces many difficulties to widespread application in longitudinal or large-scale sleep monitoring. Firstly,

Figure 2: Electrode placement in EEG [50]

the PSG monitor procedure is inherently invasive and complex, requiring many wired sensors and belts to physically attach to the patient to monitor parameters, which can restrict natural movement and cause discomfort. In addition, these physical constraints are compounded by environmental factors. This is because PSG is typically conducted in a clinical laboratory, leading to the "first-night effect" where the unfamiliar setting results in prolonged sleep latency and altered sleep architecture that may not reflect the patient's habitual sleep quality. On the other hand, some insomnia patients experience a "reverse first-night effect," sleeping better in the lab than at home, which further complicates diagnosis. Secondly, PSG is resource-intensive and costly, which needs the presence of a trained sleep technologist throughout the night and time-consuming manual scoring by specialists. This manual scoring process, typically based on 30-second epochs, introduces data resolution issues. For example, if a specific sleep stage occupies less than 50% of an epoch, it may be disregarded, potentially ignoring up to 49% of stage information. While Home Sleep Apnea Testing (HSAT) mitigates costs and access issues, the general absence of EEG recording constrains its ability to precisely characterize sleep time and architecture. This limitation often leads to an underestimated Apnea-Hypopnea Index (AHI) and challenges in identifying respiratory events associated with arousals.

2.2 Emerging Sleep Monitoring Technologies

To address the limitations of PSG regarding invasiveness, environmental constraints, and cost, wearable technologies have emerged. They aim to enable continuous, non-invasive sleep monitoring in naturalistic settings. As technological advances, these wearable devices are evolving from simple actigraphy to compact multi-sensor platforms. For general sleep-wake tracking, Liao et al. [29] developed a low-cost, open-architecture wrist-worn device that integrates motion sensing with photoplethysmography (PPG) and environmental light sensors. This multi-modal approach achieved a strong correlation ($r = 0.78$) with FDA-approved commercial actigraphy (Philips ActiWatch2), demonstrating that affordable hardware can reliably track basic sleep patterns. For the detection of specific pathologies such as Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA), smart rings have demonstrated significant clinical utility. Lu et al. [30] validated the SleepImage Ring, which utilizes Cardiopulmonary Coupling (CPC) derived from PPG signals to estimate the AHI. This device showed a high correlation ($r = 0.89$) with PSG-derived AHI and achieved an area under the curve (AUC) of 1.00 for diagnosing OSA ($AHI \geq 5$), offering a non-intrusive alternative for longitudinal screening. To bridge the gap in precise sleep staging (N1-N3/REM), ear-EEG devices have been introduced as a viable substitute for scalp-EEG. Tabar et al. [57] demonstrated that a cross-ear EEG setup could achieve a Cohen's kappa of 0.72 for five-class sleep staging, significantly outperforming wrist actigraphy (kappa = 0.21) and approaching the diagnostic fidelity of PSG for analyzing sleep architecture.

Although wearable technologies have significantly improved ambulatory monitoring, they still impose a physical burden on the user, requiring continuous wearing and regular charging. Therefore, wearable devices can still hinder long-term adherence, particularly in elderly populations or those with sensory sensitivities. To address these limitations, contactless sensing technologies have been developed to track sleep physiology with minimal intrusion. In the domain of bed-embedded sensors, Sadek et al. [52] proposed a system using a Microbend Fiber Optic Sensor (MFOS) placed under the mattress to capture Ballistocardiography (BCG) signals. Validated against PSG, this system demonstrated high accuracy for heart rate estimation (NMAE of 5.42%), although its sensitivity for detecting specific sleep apnea events was modest (about 57%). This highlights the challenges of signal-to-noise ratio in pathology detection. Further evaluating the practicality of this approach, Sadek and Abdulrazak [51] demonstrated the feasibility of such systems in real-world elderly homes, successfully tracking longitudinal sleep behaviors without user intervention, though they noted limitations in differentiating specific sleep stages like

REM versus NREM compared to clinical standards. In addition to mechanical sensing, Guettari et al. [18] explored the use of remote thermal sensors integrated into the bedroom's infrastructure. By analyzing thermal signature variations caused by body movements, this passive system achieved an 87% accuracy in classifying sleep into three aggregated states (Wake, Light Sleep, and Deep/REM Sleep). While it lacks the granularity to distinguish REM from deep sleep, its completely contactless and privacy-preserving nature makes it a promising alternative for long-term geriatric monitoring.

As new sleep monitoring technologies continue to emerge, the selection of sleep monitoring technology necessitates a strategic trade-off between diagnostic granularity and user burden, defining different application scenarios for each method. In terms of sleep staging fidelity, electrode-based wearables such as cross-ear EEG provide the highest accuracy, significantly outperforming wrist-actigraphy and approaching PSG standards for detailed architecture analysis. For pathology detection, specifically OSA, PPG-based smart rings have demonstrated superior diagnostic capability, achieving a strong correlation with PSG-derived AHI and perfect sensitivity for diagnosing mild OSA. In contrast, mechanical bed-embedded sensors, despite accurate heart rate estimation, often exhibit lower sensitivity for specific apneic events due to motion artifacts. Consequently, high-fidelity devices like Ear-EEG and smart rings work best for outpatient clinical screening and diagnostic aids, while contactless solutions perform better in long-term geriatric care and ambient assisted living, where privacy-preserving and passive monitoring is prioritized over detailed staging precision.

3 Algorithms for Sleep Staging and Micro-Event Detection

3.1 Classical Feature-Based Approaches

Researchers first used hand-crafted features and conventional machine-learning models for sleep analysis in these days [24]. Automatic sleep analysis uses preprocessed PSG or reduced sensor sets to split the night into fixed-length epochs. Automatic sleep analysis typically divides the night into fixed 30-second epochs for staging and uses shorter windows (0.5–10 s) for detecting micro-events [27]. For each segment, the system extracts features that parallel what human scorers examine. These include band-limited EEG power in the delta, theta, alpha, sigma, and beta ranges; counts of spindles and K-complexes; EOG-derived eye-movement indices; EMG-based muscle-tone measures; and statistical descriptors from respiratory and oximetry channels.

Feature vectors are commonly processed using classical machine-learning classifiers, including k-nearest neighbors (k-NN) [10], support vector machines (SVMs) [9], decision

trees [6], and random forests [5], to perform sleep-stage classification. To impose temporal consistency on the predicted labels, heuristic post-processing rules are often applied. Beyond these deterministic methods, probabilistic sequential models—such as Markov chains and hidden Markov models (HMMs) [46]—are frequently incorporated because they naturally encode valid state-transition dynamics and help produce smoother and more physiologically plausible hypnograms.

Micro-event detection in this paradigm relies on filtered energy and morphology criteria around candidate events [61]. Spindle detectors use sigma-band envelopes and duration thresholds; K-complex detectors look for large biphasic deflections; respiratory and arousal events are flagged using airflow, effort, oximetry, and EMG thresholds. These methods are computationally cheap and interpretable, but their performance degrades when confronted with heterogeneous sensors, pathologies, and large inter-subject variability, which motivated the move toward data-driven representation learning [39] [41].

3.2 Deep Learning for Sleep Staging and Micro-Event Detection

Deep learning has fundamentally transformed the methodology of automatic sleep analysis. Instead of relying on hand-crafted features, modern approaches formulate sleep staging as an end-to-end sequence learning problem. Convolutional and attention-based neural networks learn discriminative representations directly from raw or minimally processed signals, automatically identifying relevant temporal and spectral patterns within the data.

Early deep-learning approaches to automatic sleep staging typically combine a convolutional front-end with a recurrent back-end. DeepSleepNet, for example, processes raw single-channel EEG using parallel convolutional branches with different filter sizes to learn both short- and long-term temporal patterns, followed by max-pooling and fully connected layers for epoch-wise representation learning. A stack of bidirectional LSTMs then models the temporal dependencies across consecutive epochs, encoding characteristic transition dynamics between sleep stages. Trained in a two-step pre-training and fine-tuning procedure, DeepSleepNet achieves performance comparable to or exceeding hand-engineered feature methods on standard datasets such as MASS and Sleep-EDF under single-channel EEG settings [55].

SeqSleepNet extends this idea by formulating sleep staging explicitly as a sequence-to-sequence classification problem [43]. Instead of predicting labels for isolated epochs, the model takes a sequence of PSG epochs as input and jointly predicts the entire label sequence. At the epoch level, a learnable filterbank layer followed by an attention-based recurrent

layer extracts discriminative, time–frequency features. At the sequence level, a second recurrent layer operates on these epoch embeddings to capture long-range dependencies, and classification is performed at every time step of this top layer. This hierarchical recurrent architecture, trained end-to-end, yields higher overall accuracy and macro F1 scores than prior methods, particularly improving recognition of less frequent stages and producing more temporally consistent hypnograms [36, 43].

More recent work replaces recurrent components with transformer architectures that rely on self-attention to model long-range temporal structure. SleepTransformer is a sequence-to-sequence sleep-staging model built on a transformer backbone, where attention operates over sequences of epoch-level features to capture contextual information over tens of minutes [44]. Beyond competitive performance on multiple databases, the model provides attention maps at both the epoch and sequence levels that highlight salient time segments and neighboring epochs contributing to each decision, thereby improving interpretability. Additional mechanisms for entropy-based uncertainty quantification further allow low-confidence epochs to be flagged for human review, addressing clinical concerns about black-box behavior in deep learning–based sleep scoring [8, 44].

For micro-event detection, the same CNN/CNN–RNN building blocks are applied at a finer temporal resolution. A CNN or CNN–RNN architecture slides over the signal and outputs dense probabilities for sleep spindles, K-complexes, arousals, apneas, and limb movements. The SEED framework combines convolutional feature extractors with recurrent layers to detect spindles and K-complexes, and it uses a rule-based detector for pretraining to reduce the amount of manual annotation needed [58]. OxiNet, in turn, applies a one-dimensional CNN to the single-channel overnight oximetry signal to detect obstructive sleep apnea events, achieving robust performance across multiple cohorts and distribution shifts and showing that deep models can extract rich information from low-cost sensors.

Many recent systems use a multi-task formulation [28], in which a shared encoder is followed by separate task-specific heads for sleep staging, arousals, respiratory events, and limb movements. This multi-task design improves overall accuracy and produces outputs that align well with standard clinical reports [22].

Despite these gains, deep models can be data-hungry and sensitive to cohort and device shifts. Lightweight variants such as TinySleepNet and DeepSleepNet-Lite reduce parameter counts by an order of magnitude while retaining competitive performance, using careful architecture design and training schemes that are compatible with embedded deployment and uncertainty estimation.

3.3 Emerging Directions: Multimodality, Self-Supervision, and Deployable Models

Recent work has shifted the emphasis from improving accuracy on benchmark datasets to enhancing generalization across devices and populations. Achieving robust cross-device and cross-population performance has become a primary objective, motivating the use of large amounts of unlabeled data. This focus on more effective data utilization reflects a growing interest in methods that can support practical, real-world deployment, which is increasingly regarded as the next critical step for the field. There is a growing transition from traditional PSG-based analysis toward multimodal and wearable sensing. Deep multimodal architectures typically employ modality-specific encoders—such as CNNs for EEG and EOG, one-dimensional CNNs for airflow and respiratory effort, and transformer-based models for long oximetry sequences [22]. These encoders are followed by attention-based fusion mechanisms that dynamically weight each modality according to task relevance and signal quality. Meanwhile, several studies report that single-channel PPG or ECG acquired from consumer-grade wearable devices can support sleep staging and apnea screening when processed by CNN or CNN-RNN architectures [26]. These models are designed to be robust to motion-induced artifacts and can be executed on low-power embedded hardware, highlighting their suitability for practical, continuous monitoring outside the clinical environment.

Self-supervised and weakly supervised learning have emerged as effective strategies for addressing both the scarcity and variability of expert-labeled sleep data. Recent studies show that contrastive pretraining on unlabeled EEG enables models to learn discriminative sleep representations by pulling together augmented views of the same signal segment and pushing apart views from unrelated segments [21]. Common augmentations include temporal cropping, jittering, channel masking, frequency dropout, and time–frequency perturbations, which encourage robustness to noise, sensor variability, and subject-specific differences. After limited supervised fine-tuning, these models substantially narrow the performance gap to fully supervised baselines [21]. Multi-view self-supervised frameworks, such as MV-TTFC, extend this idea by jointly contrasting raw time-series signals with their time–frequency representations, improving robustness to artifacts and inter-subject variability [66]. Other approaches, including ContraWR, further enhance EEG-based SSL by tailoring augmentation pipelines and contrastive objectives to the nonstationary nature of physiological signals [62]. For event detection, weak supervision has also proven effective. Models such as SEED use rule-based detections as weak labels during pretraining and subsequently fine-tune on a

small set of expert-annotated spindles and K-complexes, substantially reducing the burden of manual annotation while maintaining competitive detection performance [58].

Building on these efforts to improve robustness and reduce reliance on expert labels, recent research increasingly focuses on model behavior under real-world variability. Cross-dataset evaluations consistently report substantial performance drops when models are applied across populations differing in age, scoring guidelines, or sensor configurations, motivating work on domain adaptation and large-scale pre-training [54]. Interpretability is similarly gaining importance: architectures such as SleepTransformer provide attention maps and entropy-based uncertainty estimates that highlight epochs requiring human review. Meanwhile, compact models like TinySleepNet deliver near-state-of-the-art accuracy with low memory and latency, enabling deployment on bedside monitors and wearable devices [56].

4 Standards, Datasets, and Clinical Validation

Standardized scoring rules, publicly available datasets, and rigorous clinical validation form the methodological foundation for modern sleep analysis. This section reviews the evolution of sleep scoring standards from classical visual manuals to contemporary AASM guidelines, surveys major open-access datasets that support benchmarking and reproducible research, and summarizes clinical validation protocols and evaluation metrics used to assess algorithm reliability.

4.1 Evolution of Sleep Scoring Standards

The earliest unified scoring framework was introduced in the 1968 Rechtschaffen and Kales (R&K) manual [47]. The R&K system defined sleep architecture using 30-second epochs and categorized sleep into wake, rapid eye movement (REM) sleep, and four non-REM (NREM) stages.

Stage identification relied on characteristic grapho-elements such as sleep spindles, K-complexes, slow-wave activity, and muscle tone changes observed through EEG, EOG, and EMG recordings. The manual provided a common language for clinical sleep diagnostics and physiological research for decades.

However, the R&K system had notable limitations: stages 3 and 4 exhibited poor inter-scorer consistency, pediatric rules were not standardized, and criteria for respiratory or arousal-related events were limited [31]. To address these challenges, the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM) introduced a revised scoring manual in 2007 [2, 4]. The AASM guidelines consolidated NREM stages 3 and 4 into a unified N3 stage, updated definitions for REM scoring, and introduced comprehensive rules for respiratory events, periodic

Figure 3: Overview of the human sleep cycle, illustrating the relative proportions of N1, N2, N3, and REM stages.

limb movements, and arousals. Subsequent revisions—such as the 2012 and 2015 editions—further harmonized adult and pediatric scoring rules [3, 17].

Comparative analyses indicate that AASM scoring yields systematically different sleep architecture compared with R&K—most notably reduced N3 duration and shifts in REM proportions [35]. For algorithm development, these differences necessitate careful dataset harmonization, particularly when combining R&K-scored and AASM-scored recordings. State-of-the-art systems therefore either train separate models for each standard or apply post-processing mappings to align outputs with the desired scoring scheme. As a result, AASM scoring has become the default “ground truth” for supervised learning in modern sleep research.

4.2 Public Datasets and Benchmarking Resources

The development of robust and generalizable sleep analysis algorithms relies heavily on high-quality, publicly accessible datasets. These datasets vary in subject demographics, sensing modalities, scoring standards, and recording environments, enabling systematic evaluation across a range of clinical and real-world conditions.

One of the earliest and most widely used resources is the Sleep-EDF and Sleep-EDF Expanded datasets [16, 23], which provide overnight EEG/EOG/EMG recordings scored using R&K rules. Their accessibility has made them foundational benchmarks for both traditional machine-learning pipelines and modern deep-learning approaches.

The Montreal Archive of Sleep Studies (MASS) [38] offers a significantly larger and more diverse PSG collection with multi-channel EEG, EOG, EMG, ECG, and respiratory signals. MASS subsets include varying montages and sampling rates, supporting research on sensor configuration,

inter-laboratory variability, and robustness across modalities. Likewise, ISRUC-Sleep [25] provides recordings from healthy subjects and clinical populations, each independently scored by multiple experts, enabling investigations into inter-scorer variability.

Large population-level cohorts include the Sleep Heart Health Study (SHHS) [45] and the MESA Sleep dataset [65], which contain home-based PSG with rich demographic and cardiovascular metadata. These datasets support research on generalization across age, ethnicity, comorbidities, and large-scale epidemiological sleep-health analyses. The Cyclic Alternating Pattern (CAP) Sleep Database [59] provides detailed EEG annotations for CAP events, supporting microstructure-level algorithm development.

More recently, multimodal datasets combining PSG with wearable-derived signals—such as photoplethysmography (PPG), accelerometry, or multi-sensor wristbands—have emerged [53]. These paired datasets enable models to be trained on high-fidelity PSG labels and deployed on lower-cost, real-world sensing modalities. They also facilitate research on domain adaptation, cross-device generalization, and the translation of clinical standards to consumer-grade devices.

Overall, these public datasets collectively support reproducible benchmarking, cross-cohort validation, ablation studies across modalities, and systematic investigation of generalization performance. However, heterogeneity in scoring standards, sensor setups, sampling rates, and subject demographics still limits direct comparison across studies, underscoring the need for standardized evaluation protocols [20].

4.3 Clinical Validation and Evaluation Metrics

Clinical validation is essential for determining whether automated sleep scoring systems achieve accuracy comparable to trained human scorers. Validation frameworks generally fall into two categories: (i) epoch-by-epoch validation and (ii) summary-measure validation.

Epoch-by-epoch validation compares predicted sleep stages or micro-events against expert annotations for each epoch. Standard evaluation metrics include overall accuracy, sensitivity (recall), specificity, precision, F1-score, and Cohen’s kappa, which accounts for chance agreement [7]. Confusion matrices highlight common misclassifications such as N1–N2 or N2–N3 transitions. Importantly, human–human agreement for AASM scoring typically ranges between 0.6 and 0.8 in Cohen’s kappa, providing an empirical ceiling for algorithm performance [42].

Summary-measure validation evaluates aggregated clinical metrics such as total sleep time (TST), sleep efficiency (SE), sleep onset latency (SOL), wake after sleep onset (WASO), and stage-distribution percentages. Bland–Altman plots are

commonly used to quantify agreement and detect systematic bias between algorithm-derived metrics and PSG ground truth [19, 53]. These analyses are especially important for wearable or contactless devices, where performance may depend on sensor placement, physiological variability, or sleep pathology.

Recent validation studies incorporate multi-center datasets, diverse populations, and cross-dataset generalization tests to evaluate robustness [60]. Regulatory-grade validation further requires reproducibility under firmware updates, stable performance across demographic subgroups, and pre-registered evaluation protocols. As automated scoring systems increasingly approach human-level performance, they are being deployed for longitudinal home monitoring, large-scale sleep epidemiology, and real-world clinical decision support.

5 Trends and Applications of Personalized Sleep Analysis

5.1 Beyond Laboratory

Recent advances in sensing technology and machine learning algorithms have pushed sleep analysis far beyond research laboratories and into homes and everyday environments. Modern sleep analysis systems now span smartphone apps, smartwatches, smart mattress, wearable devices, as well as contactless devices. These platforms detect and track movement, collect physiological data, and sense environment noises and lights during the sleep period. Such smart devices and apps provides a practical balance between accuracy, usability, and efficiency for general users [33], making long term sleep tracking feasible in daily life. Systematic reviews show that these technologies can provide a relatively accurate result in sleep tracking, although the result varies when performing different measurements. For example, many wearable devices tend to provide a more accurate measurement in heart rate and blood oxygen saturation, compared to physical activity measurements [12]. Performance might also degrade when tracking people with atypical sleep patterns [11].

In addition to wearable devices, contactless sleep monitoring technologies has been developed as an alternative to wearable devices. These systems track the breathing patterns to detect body movement. For example, contactless monitoring system tracks chest movements by detecting breathing patterns through low-power, high-frequency radio waves reflected off the person [63]. These breathing signals are then processed by a deep neural network to generate sleep hypnograms without having the user to wear any sensors. This approach is especially attractive when monitoring sensor-intolerant groups such as infants.

5.2 Trends in Personalized Sleep Analysis

In recent years, many deep learning models have been proposed for autonomous sleep analysis. To bridge the gap between controlled datasets and real world users, researchers have proposed adaptive sleep analysis algorithms. These method allow the model to learn from each individual's sensing data. For example, Zhou et al. [67] proposed an unsupervised individual domain adaption framework for sleep analysis. This model is first trained on labeled source data and have the capability to effectively adapt to new unlabeled data. This allows the model to account for individual differences. The ability to continuously monitor health metrics and make real time adjustments led to better sleep quality, physical activity, and athletic performance.

However, personalized sleep analysis also raises concerns about data privacy and security, when continuously collecting valued physiological data. Potential challenges include user data leakage, consent violations, and widespread surveillance [13]. For example, healthcare data are highly valued on the Dark Web. These unauthorized access to sensitive location, medical, and physiological data raises significant security concerns [64] In order to resolve this, various government regulations are set to protect consumer's data privacy. For example, frameworks such as California Consumer Privacy Act and US Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act are aimed to protect the balance between privacy and innovations. Furthermore, researchers have begun to develop frameworks to evaluate privacy policies of wearable devices and provide legislative guidelines.

Looking ahead, future developments of sleep analysis technology would combine advances in hardware, deep learning algorithms, and privacy preserving infrastructure. On the hardware side, it is essential to improve energy efficiency of the sensor devices. On the algorithm side, there is a growing need for more robust tracking and prediction algorithms. In parallel, combining with regulatory standards in privacy policies, personalized sleep analysis is not only accurate and adaptive, but also safe and respectful of user privacy.

6 Discussion

Our review shows that different sleep monitoring technologies each have their own advantages and distinct trade-offs in accuracy, cost, and suitability for long-term use. PSG remains the gold standard for resolving detailed sleep architecture and supporting clinical diagnosis, but its high cost and reliance on supervised laboratory settings limit scalability. On the other hand, wearable and contactless systems are more scalable and suitable for long-term use in everyday environments. However, their performance can vary substantially across devices, user characteristics, algorithms, and sensing

configurations. Taken together, these trade-offs in sleep sensing technologies suggest the importance of algorithmically extracting robust information from existing sensing devices, as well as of algorithms that adaptively learn from previous sensing data, accounting for user differences.

Deep learning has played a central role in enhancing the robustness of modern sleep monitoring technologies. Advances in model architectures have improved automatic sleep staging and movement detection, while recent work on adaptive and personalized models further extends this progress by updating model parameters using a user's sensing history across nights. These developments underscore that the accuracy and stability of sleep monitoring systems depend not only on sensor design but also on the ability of algorithms to accommodate individual variability, hardware differences, and environmental conditions. As sensing technologies continue to diversify, the generalizability of deep learning models across devices and populations will remain critical for reliable real-world deployment.

In addition to sensing and algorithmic considerations, our review of sleep scoring standards, public datasets, and validation methodologies highlights several structural challenges that shape the development of sleep analysis systems. Despite the unifying role of the AASM scoring manual, inconsistencies remain across scoring centers, datasets, and annotation protocols. These discrepancies introduce systematic differences in NREM and REM boundaries, affecting how algorithms trained on one dataset generalize to another. Public datasets such as Sleep-EDF, MASS, ISRUC, SHHS, and MESA have been instrumental in advancing algorithm development, yet they differ substantially in demographics, sensor configurations, and scoring standards. Such heterogeneity complicates cross-dataset evaluation and often leads to performance drops when models are deployed outside the distributions on which they were trained. Moreover, current clinical validation practices rely heavily on epoch-level accuracy and Cohen's kappa, which measure agreement with human scorers but do not always reflect clinical relevance. Incorporating summary-level validation—such as TST, WASO, and sleep efficiency—and statistical agreement analyses like Bland–Altman plots is therefore critical for assessing whether automated systems can be safely applied in real-world or clinical settings.

At the same time, the development of deep learning algorithms also exposes several open challenges. Deep learning models are often trained on large labeled datasets, usually obtained from past sleep research. However, performance can drop when these models are applied to new populations and devices. Addressing these gaps requires closer collaboration between algorithm designers, device designers, and clinicians to reflect user experiences.

Finally, despite advances in sleep monitoring systems, they also raise privacy and security concerns as they continuously collect physiological and behavioral data. Our review highlights the importance of privacy-preserving algorithms, such as on-device data processing, distributed learning, and secure data aggregation [15]. These approaches can reduce the need for centralized data collection. In addition, clearer regulatory frameworks and evaluation protocols are essential to balance innovation with robustness and protection of user data. Moving forward, the development of personalized sleep analysis is not only dependent on hardware and algorithm development, but also on how well these systems are integrated into user-centered everyday environments.

7 Conclusion

In this survey paper, we provide an integrated perspective on the evolution of sleep monitoring technologies, sleep scoring standards, and deep learning algorithms. We jointly cover sensing hardware, from PSG-based laboratory setups to wearable and contactless sleep-monitoring systems, as well as algorithmic advances, from handcrafted features to deep learning. Together, we show how advances in sensing hardware and algorithms jointly shape the development of modern sleep-monitoring systems. In addition, our review emphasizes that standardized scoring guidelines, public datasets, and clinical validation protocols form the methodological backbone of sleep analysis research. While the AASM scoring manual provides a unified framework, variations across datasets and annotation practices still limit cross-study comparability. Large-scale resources such as Sleep-EDF, MASS, ISRUC, SHHS, and MESA have accelerated progress, yet their heterogeneity highlights the need for harmonized benchmarks and more consistent evaluation methods. Ensuring clinical relevance further requires validation beyond epoch-level accuracy, incorporating summary measures such as TST, WASO, and sleep efficiency.

Looking ahead, progress in personalized sleep analysis will depend on coordinated advances in sensing hardware, learning algorithms, and government regulations. On the hardware side, energy-efficient sensors are needed to support long-term monitoring in everyday environments. On the algorithmic side, remaining challenges include developing robust, adaptive models that can be personalized for individual users while maintaining user privacy. With closer collaboration among clinical researchers, engineers, and regulators, personalized sleep analysis can evolve from the laboratory into a real-world product that supports healthcare monitoring and the management of sleep in everyday life.

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